

Analysis of Factors Responsible for the Rise in Cybercrime: A Study of Agbor in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria.

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Abstract: The study focused on the ‘Analysis of Factors Responsible for the Rise in Cybercrime: A Study of Agbor Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria’. The major objective of the study is to analyse the factors responsible for the rise in cybercrime in Agbor, Ika South LGA of Delta State, Nigeria. The Routine Activity Theory was used to anchor the study. The researcher used survey design and stratified random sampling methods was adopted. The population of the study is 67,610, and a sample size of 400 was chosen using Taro Yamane formula. A 5 Point Likert scale 400 questionnaires were administered on the respondents out of which 350 were found useful for analyses of the study. This shows a success rate of 87.5%. The research instrument for the study was validated by an expert in the Department of Sociology and Criminology. To determining the reliability of the research instrument, a pilot study was carried out with 30 questionnaires; the result was coded and Pearson Product Moment Statistical test was used via SPSS for analysis, and 0.82 reliability level was obtained before the instrument was used for the study. Simple percentage was used to analyse the research questions, because the study was only interested in revealing the factors that led to the rise of cybercrime. The findings of the study reveal that the factors responsible for cybercrime in Agbor, Ika South LGA of Delta State were unemployment, greed, quest to get rich quickly, easy access to the computer and weak legislations in Nigeria. The study recommended that government at all levels should provide the enabling environment for people to establish industries that would curb or at-least reduced the unemployment in Nigeria to make “yahoo-yahoo” unattractive. There is the need to train people on the concept of “small is beautiful” and on cyber security awareness programmes to protect themselves and their businesses; and the need for the Federal Government to appoint people of honesty and integrity to head the EFCC for a more effective cybercrime legislation.

Keywords: Cybercrime, Factors, Azaman, Husler’s Kingdom, Youth, Agbor

Introduction

Cybercrime is a common threat chiefly committed by cybercriminals; a set of dishonest individuals also known as yahoo-boys in Nigeria. They thrive by tricks by means of the advance fee fraud. They cunningly send out letters through facsimiles telling potential victims in other countries that they have successfully embezzled millions of dollars through corrupt means, overcharging government contracts, or other means; that they need somebody who is willing to make his or her account available for the money to be deposited, with a promise to big-heartedly compensate him or her, who unknowingly is the potential victim. Until they reach their target, it would appear that the scammers are harmless at first. Over time, the prospective victim would receive another letter asking for a little payment for processing fees. If the possible victim agrees and sent the processing fees, the money would either represent the first loss or just enough for the unsuspecting fraudster. There were not many scammers back then, but with the development of the internet, the number of scammers has increased.

In the present times, we have fraudsters popularly called yahoo yahoo-boys everywhere in Agbor Delta State, Nigeria who use the internet to defraud people. Cybercrime is a huge industry in Nigeria, especially in Agbor, Delta State. According to

Nwosu (2016) who cites Devine (2011), the introduction of the internet is what really made the Nigerian version of this ancient technique such a massive industry. With the use of cheap internet harvesting software and modern telecommunications technologies, Nigerian scammers were able to mass-email potential victims at a low cost. Over the course of the last fifteen years, the Nigerian scam has grown from a modest, local fraud operation that was effectively a cottage industry to one of the country's largest industries that is imitated worldwide. It is a contemporary technological tool that cybercriminals use to deal severe blows to their victims, which might be individuals, companies, governments, or nations.

Verma (2024) asserts that cybercrime may be more terrifying since it occurs in the background and we are only aware of it when it occurs and we are dealing with the consequences. Nigerian youths, particularly those residing in Agbor in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State, have recently turned shady and unreliable. Some of them, who are unemployed, college students, or school dropouts, have turned to the criminal profession together with their Azaman and the Husler's kingdom who are significant part of the criminal profession. The computers through the internet have evolved into tools of exploitation, providing

these young criminals with a means of earning a life through defrauding gullible people of their hard-earned money. Athekame (2024) confirmed that these young people spend their illicit fortune on ephemeral items like pricey homes, vehicles, jewelry, and cell phones. They can be found in upscale hotels, clubs, restaurants, lounges, and other establishments in large cities. They view cybercrime as a legitimate means of defrauding others.

The unsightly trend has taken a nasty turn when some parents push their kids to become better by adopting ritualistic behaviors. In order to strengthen the illicit business, some Agbor parents personally take their kids to spiritualists for spiritual fortification. In addition, some parents voluntarily hand their kids over to work as apprentice to the chairman also known as the Husler's kingdom, where they learn all sorts of cybercrime deceptive tactics in order to deceive and defraud their victims. The Agbor criminally inclined youths having learned these tactics which include online dating platforms, the art of wire-wiring (hacking business emails), investment scams where the unsuspecting victim is offered high-yield investments that promise quick profits with little to no risk, lottery scams where the scammers send messages claiming the victim has won a lottery, and online auctions where

dishonest sellers offer goods for sale at a low price to entice buyers. Sometimes they pose as celebrities, set up Facebook profiles and start businesses, or use phishing to trick their potential victims by creating SMS messages that seem to be from legitimate sources like banks, government organizations, oil companies, or communication firms. Phishing attacks aim to take advantage of people's trust in text messages by tricking them into divulging information that could result in identity theft, financial fraud, or other harmful activities. Typically, the messages are imbued with a sense of urgency, compelling gullible victims to act immediately, whether that means clicking on a malicious link, phoning a customer service number, or responding with private information. According to Athekame (2024), the attackers use a variety of strategies to make their messages seem authentic, such as copying official logos and mimicking the terminology and style of legitimate organizations. Yahoo-yahoo lads also use Bank Verification Number (BVN) scams, which involve utilizing hidden cameras to record ATM card numbers and pins in various locations, such as at the ATM using ATM skimming or at a restaurant using point-of-sale (FBI, 2011 cited in Omodunbi, Odiase, Olaniyan & Esan, 2016).

In Nigeria, the internet has also made it possible for pirated content to be distributed

illegally, freely, and virtually anonymously. They obtain "cheat codes" illegally and utilize them to obtain thousands of mobile data points and limitless airtime without paying for them. They may be acting in these ways merely because they are unemployed, exploiting computer vulnerabilities and lax cyber laws, and being avaricious and desperate to make illegal money and become wealthy overnight. They may also be appealing to girls and other young people who are influenced by them and aspire to be like them.

Attempts were made by government to curb the cybercrime menace through several legislations such as the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission Act (2004), the Criminal Code Cap. C 28 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria (2004), the Penal Code (1959), the Advance Fee Fraud and other Related Offences Acts (2006), 2015 Cybercrime Act, including the newly Nigeria Cybercrimes Act 2024 which addressed the gaps in the 2015 Act (Hannatu, 2025). In spite of these Acts meant to address cybercrimes in Nigeria, the perpetrators of cybercrimes continue to increase and advanced in their fraudulent practices, and this may be due to the faceless nature of the crimes; thus, giving credence to this study of analysing the factors responsible for the rise in cybercrime in Agbor, in Ika South Local Government Area

(LGA) of Delta State, Nigeria in order to find lasting solution to the menace.

Objectives of the Study

The major objective of the study is to analyse the factors responsible for the rise in cybercrime in Agbor in Ika South LGA of Delta State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were asked to guide the study:

- i. Is unemployment one of the factors responsible for the rise in cybercrime in Agbor, Ika South LGA of Delta State, Nigeria?
- ii. Can greed trigger the rise in cybercrime in Agbor, Ika South LGA of Delta State, Nigeria?
- iii. Does the quest for wealth lead to the rise in cybercrime in Agbor, Ika South LGA of Delta State, Nigeria?
- iv. Can the vulnerability of the computer leads to the rise in cybercrime in Agbor, in Ika South LGA of Delta State, Nigeria?
- v. How has weak legislation contributed to the rise in cybercrime in Agbor, in Ika South LGA of Delta State, Nigeria?

Conceptual Framework

i. Concept of Cybercrime

Cybercrime is not universally defined. Nonetheless, we have formulated the idea in accordance with the opinions of the following academics: Brush and Cobb (2020) conceptualize cybercrime as any illegal activity involving a computer, network, or network device. Similarly, Sushmith (2023) states that cybercrime is any action that uses a computer or computer network to carry out tasks like obtaining unauthorized access to data. Furthermore, Proofpoint (2025) define cybercrime as broad phrase that encompasses a wide range of illegal activities conducted through the use of a computer, network, or other digital devices. Cybercriminals engage in a wide variety of illicit activities. These illegal activities include ransomware, virus assaults, identity theft, and phishing. The majority of cybercriminals use the network to distribute malware, illicit information, photos, or other materials, while some use it to harm or disable computers. The primary purpose of cybercrimes in Agbor, Delta State, is financial gain.

ii. Factors

Vocabulary.com (2025) conceptualise factors as anything that contributes casually to a result. In other words, factors are elements that influences something. In this study, factors refer to causes such as factors responsible for cybercrime or factors that causes cybercrime to happen.

iii. Concept of Azaman

Azaman' is the middle man who owns the account or knows the means of pulling out the illicit money. Wherever the stolen money is, the Azaman goes there and help the yahoo boy (s) to launder the money and in turn collects his percentage. In order words, the Azaman also known as "gatekeeper" is a professional intermediary involved in facilitating the transfer of the illegal proceeds across borders, making the Azaman to the illegal financial system wittingly or unwittingly assist in obfuscating the true source of funds using a dizzy array of legal vehicles and jurisdictions (Cooly & Sharman, 2017). The Azaman is the middle man who owns the account or knows the means of pulling out the illicit money. Wherever the stolen money is, the Azaman goes there and help the yahoo boy (s) to launder the money and in turn collects his percentage.

iv. Huslers Kingdom (HK)

This refers to the school or office where prospective or would be yahoo boys are trained or serve as apprentice under the tutelage of the deadly swindler also known as the “Hustlers Kingdom” (HK) Chairman (the boss of the fraudulent school or office).

v. Concept of Youth

When it comes to the concept of youth, different opinions exist. It has been defined by several organisations and scholars, all of which have some degree of differences in what they consider to be the exact meaning of youth. Mazarin (2016) conceptualise youth as a period which begins at age 15 and ends at age 40. Anaechie (2018) states that youth are fluid category than a fixed age group. Age is the easiest way to define this group particularly in relation to education and employment. Youth is often indicated as a person between the age where he/she may leave compulsory education, and the age at which he/she finds his/her employment; this later age limit has been increasing, as high levels of unemployment and the cost of setting up an independent household put many young people into a prolong period of dependency. Youth in Nigeria are young people between the ages of 18-35years and are inevitably characterises by always wanting to be with peers, anxious of the future (curiosity), perfect vessel of

information, desire for independence and authority and are more energetic. In this study, youth refers to young people between the ages of 15 – 35 years.

Theoretical Framework

Routine Activity Theory

The study is anchored by the Routine Activity Theory propounded by Cohen and Felson (1979). The Routine Activity Theory is the most appropriate framework for understanding Nigerian youth engagement in cybercrime. The theory states that for a crime to be committed, the victim and the criminal must meet at a specific location and time, and in the absence of effective guardian. Here, the perpetrator and the victims of cybercrime communicate online. It is implied that when the perpetrator is working online and the victim(s) appears to be naive, the perpetrator detects a loophole and strikes. Though, these may not be the main reasons for cybercrime but the criminal may be driven to strike by their desperation and unemployment status or other reasons. The Routine Activity Theory offers effective explanation for the root causes of the crime. The offender is prompted to prey on the desirable targets when there is little or no control. It implies that lowering

criminal chances contributes to a decrease in cybercrime.

Meier and Meithe (1993) cited in Nwosu (2016) asserts that criminals make logical decisions in selecting victims that would give them large return with least danger and without exerting much energy. The theory is therefore predicated on the idea that criminals seek opportunities to obtain what they want through illegal means. Opportunities are necessary for cybercrime to occur. Though, a determined criminal is required to commit cybercrime, it is not always sufficient; but some young Nigerians without jobs, especially in Agbor are motivated criminals who use the internet to communicate with some innocent people, take advantage of their gullibility or opportunity created and dupe them.

Empirical Study

Factors Responsible for the rise in Cybercrimes

i. Cybercrime and Unemployment

A study by Ihediora (2020) looks at cybercrime and unemployment in Delta State, Nigeria's Ughelli North Local Government Area. The study's goal was to find out how much unemployment in Delta State's Ughelli North Local Government Area contributes to

or causes cybercrime. The sociological theory of crime was used in the study. 147 people were chosen as the sample size. Respondents were chosen using questionnaires and in-depth interviews. Three research questions were raised. The descriptive approach was used to analyze the data that addressed the study questions. The study's conclusions include the following: cybercrime is present, unemployment is a significant contributing factor to cybercrime, and unemployment itself is present. The study recommended that frequent awareness campaigns should be conducted via mass media, including radio, television, places of worship, and even the general public, to highlight and deter those who plan to engage in cybercrime. Laws that specify punishments for anyone found guilty of any crime, particularly cybercrime, should be passed by the federal, state, and local governments. Similarly,

Nnadozie (2024) looked into the threat of an increase in cybercrime among young people in Nigeria as well as ways to secure computer devices. The nine-question questionnaire used in the study was given to 78 willing, well-educated members of the working class. The descriptive method was also used in the study to analyze the data. Among other things, the study's main conclusions included the idea that the growing incidence of cybercrime among young people in society was due to a

lack of work. Additionally, Hassan, Lass, and Makinde (2012) emphasize that over 20 million Nigerian graduates lack productive job, making unemployment one of the main reasons of cybercrime in the country. As a result, they are now more likely to turn to cybercrime as a source of income.

ii. *Cybercrime and Greed*

Karma (2023) admits that people's greed has been the main cause of the recent increase in cybercrimes, which are easier than traditional robberies. The fraudsters exploit people's lack of knowledge about cyber mechanisms, which makes it simple for them to steal their money. In a similar vein, Adesulu (2017) claims that Babatope Longe saw and defined cybercrime and cybervictimization as crimes that are linked to the investigation of human weaknesses like greed, credulity, and the wild pursuit of wealth syndrome rather than crimes that are inevitably impacted by social factors like unemployment, poverty, and inequality.

Furthermore, Nogofallmaga (2023) state that cybercriminals use victims' greed to influence them to take actions that will benefit the criminal; greed can make people more susceptible to manipulation by cybercriminals who offer financial gain or rewards in exchange for personal or financial

information; cybercriminals frequently pair it with a need, meaning they are aware of their targets' desires and use those desires as bait; and such greed impairs judgment and causes people to ignore warning signs or red flags that indicate a scam.

iii. *Cybercrime and Quest for wealth*

Usman and Sabo (2024) investigated Nigerian cybercrime's societal reasons. Using secondary data gathering techniques, the study found that the pursuit of wealth is one of the social factors contributing to cybercrime in Nigeria. Among other things, the report suggested that there should be more job opportunities, particularly for young people, and that the wealth gap should be closed by allocating resources fairly. Similarly, Hassan et al. (2012) claim that Nigerian cybercrime is a result of the pursuit of wealth. Because today's youth are so avaricious and unprepared to start small, they resort to cybercrimes in an attempt to catch up to their wealthier peers.

iv. *Cybercrime and Vulnerability of the Computer*

According to Krazytech (2017), computer vulnerabilities make it simple for hackers to obtain private data. Access codes, relina

pictures, and other materials that can readily trick biometric systems and get past firewalls can be stolen by hackers and used to get around a variety of security measures. Because cybercriminals are anonymous, it can be challenging to apprehend them, and when you do, proof of the crime may be readily removed. This is now a prevalent and evident issue that paralyzes the system that investigates cybercrimes.

v. Cybercrime and Weak Legislation

According to Hassan et al. (2012), the absence of strong legislation against cybercrime encourages criminals to commit more crimes since they know they will never be caught. Sibe and Kaunert (2024) identified a few of the Cybercrime Act of 2015's shortcomings. Penalties for convictions of computer-related fraud are outlined in Section 14(1) – (5) of the Cybercrimes (Prohibition, Prevention, Etc.) Act, 2015. For the various cases, the punishments range from 3 to 7 years in prison or a fine of ₦5 to ₦10 million. The problem with this is that since 2015, the value of the Naira has drastically declined. As a result, the punishment has been significantly lowered in monetary terms. Remember that because cybercrime is a cross-border activity, the majority of its profits in Nigeria are in US dollars. In terms of a real-world example, \$1

was worth N181.78, and in April 2024, it was worth ₦1,297.33. Therefore, a cybercriminal who was found guilty of computer-related fraud in 2015 and fined ₦5 million would have paid \$27,505.78. A cybercriminal found guilty of the same crime in 2024 would have to pay \$3,854.07. The result is a lower punishment because the majority of cybercrime proceeds in Nigeria are in dollars.

From a different angle, inflationary pressure has gradually reduced the value of the Naira and, consequently, the fine option's worth. For example, the 12-month average inflation rate for all items was 8.76% in 2015; by February 2024, it had risen to 31.70%. Penalties are supposed to deter crime, but in this case, the macroeconomic and monetary volatility over time has given the impression that the cybercriminal is being encouraged. This is a clear illustration of a situation where regulation was inadequate and based on static assumptions rather than practical variables that reflected changing dynamics.

Methodology

The study used survey design. This enables the researchers to gather meaningful data on the phenomenon for the purpose of reliability and generalization. The population of the study is 67,610 (GeoName geographical

database, 2024), and a sample size of 400 was chosen using Taro Yamane formula. Stratified random sampling methods was adopted. A 5 Point Likert scale of 400 questionnaires was administered on the respondents out of which 350 were found useful for analyses. The research instrument was validated by an expert in the Department of Sociology and Criminology, while the reliability of the instrument was carried out with 30 questionnaires; the result obtained was 0.82 reliability level using Pearson Product Moment Statistical test; and Simple percentage (%) was used to analyse the research questions because the researchers

were only interested in finding out the factors or causes responsible for the rise in cybercrime in Agbor, Ika South LGA of Delta State Nigeria.

Data Presentation and Discussion of Findings

For the purpose of analysing the research questions, each question was changed to statement. Responses such as: Agreed and Seriously Agreed were regarded as “Agreed”; Disagreed and Seriously Disagreed were regarded as “Disagreed” and responses for Neutral remained as “Neutral”.

Table I: Unemployment is one of the factors responsible for the rise in cybercrime in Agbor, Ika South LGA of Delta State, Nigeria?

Cybercrime and Unemployment	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Agreed	344	98.2
Disagreed	3	0.9
Neutral	3	0.9
Total	350	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The findings of the study reveals that a small percentage of the respondents comprising 0.9% disagreed that unemployment is not a factor responsible for cybercrime, and 0.9% of the respondents are neutral, while majority of the respondents comprising 98.2% agreed that unemployment is a major factor responsible for the rise in cybercrime in

Agbor, in Ika South LGA of Delta State, Nigeria. The findings agree with the works of Ihediora (2020) who examined the relationship between unemployment and cybercrime in Ughelli North Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria and that of Ebimiedei, Eromhonsele and Mezieuzor (2023) who examined the

dynamics of the emerging problem of unemployment and cybercrime in South-East

and South-South Geo-political zones in Nigeria

Table II: Greed triggers the rise in cybercrime in Agbor, Ika South LGA of Delta State, Nigeria?

Cybercrime and Greed	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Agreed	343	98.0
Disagreed	5	1.42
Neutral	2	0.5
Total	350	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The findings of the study indicate that majority of the respondents comprising 98.0% agreed that greed triggers the rise in cybercrime in Agbor, Ika South LGA of Delta State, Nigeria. The findings is in agreement with the work of Karma (2023) who asserts that fraudsters take advantage of people's ignorance of cyber mechanisms and their greed makes it easy to rob them of their

money; and that of Nogofallmaga (2023) who reported that cybercriminals use victims greed to persuade them to take action that benefits the criminal; that greed can make people vulnerable to manipulation by cybercriminals who promise financial gain or rewards in exchange for personal or financial information.

Table III: The quest for wealth led to the rise in cybercrime in Agbor, Ika South LGA of Delta State, Nigeria?

Cybercrime and Quest for Wealth	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Agreed	342	97.7
Disagreed	6	1.7
Neutral	2	0.5

Total	350	100
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Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The data shows that 1.7% of the respondents disagreed that the quest for wealth led to the rise in cybercrime, and 0.5% are neutral. However, majority of the respondents comprising 97.7% agreed that the quest for wealth by all means possible led to the rise in cybercrime in Agbor, in Ika LGA of Delta State, Nigeria. The findings agree with the

works of scholars such as Usman and Sabo (2024) and that of Hassan et-al (2012) that reveals that one of the social causes of cybercrime in Nigeria is the quest for wealth; because youths of nowadays are very greedy, they are not ready to start small hence they strive to level up with their rich counterparts by engaging in cybercrimes.

Table IV: Vulnerability of the computer led to the rise in cybercrime in Agbor, Ika South LGA of Delta State, Nigeria?

Cybercrime and Vulnerability of the Computer	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Agreed	340	97.1
Disagreed	7	2.0
Neutral	3	0.9
Total	350	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The findings of the research show that out of the 350 respondents used for the analysis of the study 340 respondents, representing 97.1% agreed that the vulnerability of the computer led to the rise in cybercrime. The

computer is easily accessible to both literate and illiterates in society. The findings agree with the work of Krazytech (2017) that says computer vulnerabilities make it simple for hackers to obtain private sensitive data.

Table V: Weak legislation led to the rise in cybercrime in Agbor, Ika South LGA of Delta State, Nigeria?

Cybercrime and weak legislation	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Agreed	342	97.7

Disagreed	5	1.42
Neutral	3	0.9
Total	350	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The findings of the research show that out of the 350 respondents used for the analysis of the study 342 respondents, representing 97.7% agreed that weak legislations led to the rise in cybercrime in Agbor, Ika South LGA of Delta State, Nigeria. The Legislations are weak because none has been able to curb cybercrime. The findings agree with the works of Hassan, et al (2012) which states that, the lack or weak cybercrime laws encourage the perpetrators of cybercrime to commit more crime knowing that they can always go uncaught and that of Sibe and

Kaunert (2024) who pointed out some of the weak aspects of the Cybercrime Act 2015.

The findings of the study were confirmed and supported by the works of scholars reviewed. This makes the study unique and scientific, and the objectives of the study were achieved. The contribution of the study to knowledge was that the study was able to establish that the factors or rather causes of cybercrime in Agbor, Ika South LGA of Delta State were unemployment, greed, quest to get rich quickly, easy access to the computer and weak legislations in Nigeria.

Conclusion

Cybercrime is a huge problem to Nigeria and Nigerians who constitute part of victims. The perpetrators of cybercrime thrive on tricks. The scammers used to be few in Agbor, but today there is growing number of them due to the availability of computers and internet on mobile phones. In the present times, we have fraudsters popularly called yahoo-yahoo boys everywhere in Agbor Delta State, Nigeria who use the internet to defraud people. Cybercrime is a huge industry currently in Agbor, Ika South LGA of Delta State.

The most painful aspect is that many Nigerian youth are perpetrators of cybercrimes, especially those of them that lives in Agbor. They have become chancy and not to be trusted. Some of them that are school dropouts, undergraduates and the unemployed have taken to the criminal occupation 'Yahoo Yahoo' also known as Cybercrime. The perpetrators of cybercrime include the Azaman the middle man who owns the account used in pulling out the illicit money, while the 'Hustlers Kingdom' (HK) is the Chairman of the yahoo yahoo-boys (the boss of the fraudulent office where yahoo yahoo-boys are tutored). These scenarios are reality

in Agbor - a town in Ika South Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria.

Attempts were made by government to curb the cybercrime menace through several legislations but none seemed to work effectively, as the perpetrators of cybercrime continue to increase and advanced in the fraudulent act, and this may be due to the faceless nature of the crimes; thus, giving credence to this study - analysis of factors responsible for the rise in cybercrime in Agbor, Ika South Local Government Area (LGA) of Delta State, Nigeria in order to find lasting solution to the menace, which has been done in the preceding recommendations.

Recommendations

The following are recommended:

i. Government at all levels in Nigeria should provide the enabling environment for people

to establish industries that would curb or at least reduced the unemployment situation so as to make yahoo-yahoo unattractive.

ii. There is need to train people on the concept of “small is beautiful”, that is to appreciate the

little you have. This training will go a long way in reducing greed and the quest for quick wealth without commensurate hard work.

iii. The fact that access to the computer has become too easy and deceitful instrument used by the cybercriminals, the public should stay informed by attending cyber security awareness programmes to protect themselves and their businesses.

iv. The Federal government of Nigeria should appoint people of honesty and integrity to head the EFCC for a more effective legislation.

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